
MARKETING STRATEGIC PLANNING AS A FUNDAMENTAL TOOL FOR LANGUAGE SCHOOLS

[Ciências Sociais Aplicadas, Edição 120 MAR/23 SUMÁRIO / 30/03/2023](#)

REGISTRO DOI:10.5281/zenodo.11118139

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SUMMARY

The present study aims to analyze the guidelines for the effective implementation of strategic marketing planning in language schools. Strategic marketing planning plays a crucial role in the success of educational institutions, especially in the language education sector, where competition is intense and the demand for language courses is growing. The lack of strategic direction can lead to resource wastage and missed growth opportunities. Therefore, it is essential to adopt guidelines that assist in the effective implementation of strategic marketing planning. In this study, key guidelines were identified based on a comprehensive literature review. These guidelines include clear definition of organizational objectives, market analysis, market segmentation, value proposition definition, integration of marketing strategies, result measurement, establishment of an efficient management system, internal communication, and pursuit of innovation. The methodology adopted consisted of reviewing scientific articles and relevant

publications. The analysis of the studies revealed that the effective implementation of these guidelines contributes to the success of marketing strategies in language schools by enhancing their ability to attract, retain, and meet the needs of students. The guidelines provide a clear roadmap for defining measurable objectives, understanding the target market, developing differentiated value propositions, coordinating marketing actions, evaluating performance, and continuous improvement. In conclusion, the effective implementation of strategic marketing planning in language schools is a key factor for their success and growth. The adoption of the guidelines identified in this study provides a solid foundation for the development and execution of efficient marketing strategies. These guidelines assist language schools in positioning themselves competitively in the market, acquiring and retaining students, and ensuring long-term sustainable growth.

Keywords: strategic marketing planning, language schools, guidelines, effective implementation, competitiveness.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the current context, marked by intense competition and constant search for differentiation, language schools face the challenge of attracting and retaining students in an increasingly competitive market. In this scenario, strategic marketing planning emerges as a fundamental tool for these institutions, helping to define clear objectives, identify market opportunities and formulate efficient strategies to achieve success.

This work focuses on strategic marketing planning applied specifically to language schools. Among the various teaching institutions, language schools play a crucial role in training professionals and expanding personal horizons. Therefore, understanding how strategic marketing planning can contribute to the success of these schools becomes a matter of great relevance and interest.

Given the aforementioned context, the following problem arises: how can strategic marketing planning be used as a fundamental tool to boost the growth and competitiveness of language schools? This issue leads us to reflect on the importance of strategic marketing planning and its potential benefits for the language education sector.

The general objective of this work is to analyze the role of strategic marketing planning as a fundamental tool for language schools. To achieve this objective, the following specific objectives are proposed: conceptualize marketing; identify the main elements of strategic marketing planning applicable to language schools and propose guidelines for the effective implementation of strategic marketing planning in language schools.

This work is justified by the need to understand and explore the potential of strategic marketing planning as an indispensable tool for language schools. The growing competitiveness in this sector demands a strategic and market-oriented approach, capable of providing differentiation and competitive advantage to educational institutions.

The methodology adopted in this work will consist of a comprehensive bibliographic review, based on reliable and updated sources, such as books, scientific articles and academic research. This approach will allow an in-depth analysis on the subject of strategic marketing planning applied to language schools, providing theoretical and practical basis for the proposed investigation.

2. DEVELOPMENT

2.1. MARKETING

Marketing and advertising proves to be a challenge for everyone. The narrative behind each product is fascinating, with marketing providing a commercial, cultural, historical and emotional context for it. The impact of this branch on individuals and society is growing, as their preferences and

even their needs are influenced by it, even if many people do not know it (GARCIA, 2004). Communication, advertising and marketing, although distinct, operate collaboratively to promote a brand, service, product or idea.

As defined by Garcia in 2004, marketing is the fundamental link between customer demands and a company's offers; aims to deliver the most appropriate product, in the most opportune place, at the most advantageous time.

By studying consumer behavior and conducting market research, companies seek to assess individuals' needs and assess the state of the market. The ultimate goal is to identify gaps and adapt offerings to meet customer expectations. According to KOTLER, marketing is a social and managerial process aimed at satisfying desires and needs, enabling the creation and exchange of products and values between individuals and groups (KOTLER, 1998 p. 3).

Marketers have an alternative approach to encouraging their target audience to buy a specific product or adopt a specific idea. This method focuses on four levers, known as the "4P": Product highlighting its unique selling points and benefits; Price aligned with the value of the product; Positioning of distribution channels; and, Promotion through communication. These four elements combine to formulate the ideal mix that constitutes the offer, as defined by Pereira et al. (2009).

The authors suggest that communication is an indispensable marketing tool that involves the transmission of messages to customers. This covers brand or product promotion as well as attracting and retaining customers. To achieve these objectives, communication relies on two different means: mass media and non-media channels.

The objective of media communication is to disseminate a message to a wide audience, usually through conventional channels such as television, radio, print and billboards. On the other hand, non-media communication

is more individualized, encompassing personalized and targeted actions such as direct marketing, events, social networks and sales promotions, as observed by Pereira et al. (2009).

From the perspective of Garcia (2004), advertising is part of the mass media, allowing the dissemination of promotional messages to a wide audience. While typically centered around a product and its attributes, the message also encompasses the brand's values. While advertising is critical to achieving marketing objectives, it is important to note that marketing, communication, and advertising are distinct entities that interconnect to achieve common objectives.

Prior to 1950, marketing did not exist as such, however, marketing practices emerged from the industrial revolution (1850-1939). Initially, there was only the sales function to adjust the flow of a small production to a sufficient demand, in a local and uncompetitive environment (LIMA et al., 2009). Later, according to Lima et al (2009), technical advances and advances in transportation led to growth in production and the market. Thus, companies that aim to sell more products in relation to a financially weakened demand in a more competitive national market, begin to disclose research to know which region to target and by extension of geographic and sociocultural segmentation. The expansion of sales and the increase in offer for the same product also reveal brand identity and packaging. Designed to make the product recognizable and transportable, it becomes synonymous with guarantee and quality.

Marketing was born at the beginning of the 20th century when the market economy was widespread in the western world. This new system radically transformed the relationship between economy and society, giving economic activities a previously unimaginable autonomy. The existing relationships between producers, workers and consumers would, from then on, be governed by market laws and no longer by social control (CHAUVEL, 2001 p. 93).

The concept of marketing was born during the period around the second world war. First, the creation of the AMA (American Marketing Association) in 1937 normalizes and spreads the discipline. Then, between 1950 and 1960, in a context of mass production and globalization, companies are starting to consider customer expectations, since the only way to maximize profits is to produce what will be consumed (GARCIA, 2004). From then on, according to Garcia (2004), marketing continues to place the customer more and more at the center of concerns. Thus, the 1960s are characterized by the behavioral study of consumers. The 1970s introduced the concept of customer king. So, you gradually notice the emergence of today's marketing, that is, a very targeted and almost individual customer relationship.

The progress of marketing occurred in the centralization of functions. Before the industrial revolution, marketing functions were under the control of various company departments such as finance. But starting in the 1940s, all existing marketing functions are placed under the authority of one person whose purpose is to better sell a given amount of product. Today, the marketing function is very important in an organization, so much so that some companies are coordinating all their departments with marketing requirements. This structure is justified by the fact that certain markets would not exist without good marketing work (LIMA et al, 2009).

Likewise, financial efforts in marketing have come a long way. Before the industrial revolution, they represented less than 9% of the payroll, while that number rose to over 40% in 1950. Today, marketing expenses vary from one structure to another and are revised to decline as they exist. new low-cost methods, such as social media, to reach large numbers of consumers. Thus, although marketing modeling dates back to the Second World War period, it can be considered that marketing was born in 1850 with the industrial revolution. This department has become increasingly important in companies and dedicated investments have increased considerably since 1950. Today, new technologies have revisited

traditional marketing that has gone from mass marketing 1.0 to marketing 3.0, comprising a range of methods whose target is each increasingly specific (LIMA et al, 2009).

Instead of treating people simply as consumers, in Marketing 3.0 marketers treat them as full human beings: with mind, heart and spirit. More and more consumers are looking for solutions to satisfy their desire to transform the globalized world into a better world. [...] They seek not only functional and emotional satisfaction, but also spiritual satisfaction, in the products and services they choose (ACHROL; KOTLER, 2012 p. 12).

Anyway, marketing is the branch of a company that is interested in the wants and needs of customers. Linked to communication and advertising through a subsidiary relationship, these notions must be distinguished. Furthermore, under the impetus of the industrial revolution, marketing appears on the economic table as early as 1870 and its place in companies today is undeniable and capital. It should also be added that this discipline easily adapts to the managerial and technological trends of each era. As a result, it is constantly evolving (LIMA et al, 2009).

The concept of relationship marketing is centered on building personalized and ongoing relationships with individual customers. This approach aims to support customers throughout the purchase and loyalty process. Unlike transactional marketing, which prioritizes the product and the shopping experience, relationship marketing is completely customer centric. (BRAMBILLA et al., 2010)

Although not an ancient practice, Relationship Marketing has become a fundamental aspect of customer-focused corporations since its emergence in the early 1980s. Its origins lie in the ever-evolving nature of consumer preferences, which requires adaptation. constant by organizations. As consumer expectations continue to evolve, the need for closer relationships between companies and their customers becomes

more evident. The main objective of Relationship Marketing is to build a loyal and profitable customer base, as stated by Brambilla (2008).

Relationship marketing strives to cultivate and enhance business connections between a company and its customers. Marketers prioritize the quality, durability, substance, and value of the customer relationship in individual interactions. This approach emerges from customer relationship management (CRM), as noted by Brambilla et al. (2010).

The authors postulate that Relationship Marketing involves cultivating long-term business relationships with customers, adopting a lifecycle approach, instead of focusing only on campaigns or specific actions. This strategy prioritizes creating, maintaining, and developing customer relationships over time.

The ultimate goal is to move customers along a spectrum, starting with their point of view, moving from casual shopper to diligent worker, and finally from mere consumer to passionate advocate. The tools used by marketing managers remain consistent, utilizing targeted media such as email, social media, the web, direct mail, telemarketing, text messaging and mobile apps. At the same time, the focus remains on identifying customers in both scenarios.

In terms of content and function, the contrast between these media is stark. While both can promote products, relationship marketing media differentiates itself by offering a unique blend of informational and promotional materials. Examples of such materials include guides, video clips, and newsletters that increase advertiser credibility and work to establish a sense of rapport with the customer. (BRAMBILLA et al., 2010).

As the studies by Brambilla et al. (2010) indicate, such interactions can help customers select the ideal product or service that aligns with their preferences, conduct and qualities. Additionally, educating customers on how to get the most out of your product can increase your satisfaction rates and overall customer experience.

In the past, mass marketing was the strategy to reach the maximum number of customers for a product. However, in modern times, relationship marketing takes precedence. Emphasizes engagement with customers to develop a unique set of values that meet their specific needs, with the aim of achieving customer satisfaction and promoting lasting relationships with the company (MADRUGA, 2006).

In the past, relationship marketing thrived on the concept of being responsive. However, with the emergence of social media and its interactive capabilities, the focus has shifted to promoting dialogue. In today's world, customers can interact with advertisers in real time, express their comments in public forums and impact the perception and satisfaction of others in the community (BLUME, 2005).

Unlike transactional marketing, relational marketing goes beyond customer identification and seeks to understand their behavior and demographics. This insight is largely derived from comprehensive assessments of your past buying habits. In cases where new customers are acquired and their buying patterns are unknown, media affinity and the level of interest in the advertiser's product or service category are studied (BLUME, 2005).

In relationship marketing, loyalty is an important consideration, as the author explains. While loyalty programs that incentivize customers with rewards are often associated with this concept, they are not an absolute requirement. Loyalty schemes mainly serve to identify customers and study their buying patterns. However, if we already have a clear understanding of our customers and their purchasing behavior, such a program may not be imperative.

As a company meets the needs, wants, and expectations of its customers, it lays the groundwork for creating a mutually beneficial relationship. This paves the way for customer loyalty through a

relationship of shared interests. Ultimately, relationship marketing puts customer satisfaction and loyalty at the forefront of its objectives.

The marketing concept dictates that, to prosper, a company must outperform competitors in satisfying customers with superior value propositions. Marketing professionals must not only meet the demands of target consumers, but also establish strategic advantages by positioning their products or services in relation to competing alternatives (SOUZA, 2009).

To promote loyalty, effective communication, quality customer experiences and timely advertiser presence are essential. Brambilla et al. (2010) suggest that three ingredients are needed to cultivate strong and lasting relationships: customer knowledge, emotional resonance with the brand message, and customer trust in the brand. When these criteria are met, relationships flourish in a healthy and sustainable way.

2.2. THE MAIN ELEMENTS OF STRATEGIC MARKETING PLANNING APPLICABLE TO LANGUAGE SCHOOLS

Strategic marketing planning is an essential approach for language schools, as it helps define guidelines and actions aimed at achieving organizational objectives efficiently and competitively. In this context, it is fundamental to understand the main elements of this process, in order to apply them properly and obtain satisfactory results.

One of the key elements of strategic marketing planning for language schools is market analysis. According to Kotler et al. (2018), this step consists of identifying and understanding the needs, desires, and behaviors of consumers, as well as analyzing the competition and market trends. Through this analysis, the language school can identify opportunities and threats, adapt its offer to the demands of the target audience and position itself differently in relation to competitors.

Another important element is the definition of the target audience. According to Churchill and Peter (2020), knowing the profile and characteristics of potential students is essential to direct marketing strategies. A language school can segment its target audience according to criteria such as age group, education level, interests, and motivations for language learning. Based on this segmentation, it is possible to develop more targeted and effective marketing actions.

In strategic marketing planning, it is crucial to establish clear and measurable objectives. As cited by Ferrell and Hartline (2021), objectives must be specific, achievable, relevant and time-bound, allowing the language school to assess the progress of its strategies and make decisions based on performance indicators. For example, a goal might be to increase enrollment by 20% in a given period.

The definition of the value offer is also a central element. According to Kotler and Keller (2019), the language school must identify the benefits and competitive advantages it offers students in relation to other institutions. It can be a differentiated teaching methodology, highly qualified teachers, a wide variety of languages or exchange programs. This value proposition must be communicated clearly and persuasively in all marketing efforts.

In the digital context, strategic marketing planning should also consider the online presence of the language school. According to Chaffey and Ellis-Chadwick (2020), it is essential to have a digital marketing strategy that includes the creation of an institutional website, the use of social networks, email marketing campaigns and monitoring of online reputation. The proper use of digital tools can increase the school's visibility, attract new students, and strengthen relationships with current ones.

Communication is a transversal element in all strategic marketing planning. According to Parente (2021), it is essential to establish effective

and consistent communication, both internally and externally. This includes the development of a visual identity and a coherent institutional message, the elaboration of attractive communication materials, the promotion of events and strategic partnerships, as well as the frequent interaction with students and potential students.

In addition to the elements mentioned, other aspects can be considered in strategic marketing planning for language schools. Among them, we highlight the monitoring of student satisfaction, the continuous evaluation and improvement of teaching programs, the efficient management of financial and human resources, the establishment of partnerships with companies and institutions, participation in fairs and events in the sector, between others.

2.3. GUIDELINES FOR THE EFFECTIVE IMPLEMENTATION OF STRATEGIC MARKETING PLANNING IN LANGUAGE SCHOOLS

The effective implementation of strategic marketing planning in language schools requires the adoption of specific guidelines that help to obtain positive results. Several studies have addressed these guidelines, highlighting fundamental practices and recommendations for the successful implementation of strategic marketing planning in educational institutions.

One of the essential aspects is the clear definition of organizational objectives. As mentioned by Kotler et al. (2018), objectives must be measurable, realistic and aligned with the mission and vision of the language school. These objectives may involve increasing enrollment, improving student retention, strengthening the brand, or expanding into new markets. By establishing clear objectives, the institution will have a clear direction to direct its marketing strategies.

Market analysis is another key element to the effective implementation of strategic marketing planning. According to Ferrell and Hartline (2021), it is essential to understand the characteristics and needs of the target

audience, identify market trends, assess competition, and identify opportunities for differentiation. This analysis allows the language school to adjust its marketing strategies according to market demands and maximize its chances of success.

Market segmentation also plays a key role in implementing strategic marketing planning. According to Churchill and Peter (2020), when segmenting the market, the language school identifies specific groups of consumers with similar needs and characteristics. This allows the institution to develop targeted and personalized marketing strategies to meet the needs of each segment. For example, you can segment the market by age group, specific interests, or learning needs.

The clear definition of the value proposition is another crucial aspect. Kotler and Keller (2019) emphasize that the language school must clearly identify and communicate the benefits and differentials it offers to students. It could be an innovative teaching methodology, qualified teachers, a wide variety of languages or exchange programs. It is important to highlight and promote these distinctive attributes to attract and retain students.

The integration of marketing strategies is also a key element for the effective implementation of strategic planning. As mentioned by Parente (2021), it is essential to ensure that all marketing actions are aligned and work synergistically. This involves the coordination of offline and online strategies, the consistent use of the visual identity and institutional message, and the integration of communication actions, such as advertising, events and digital marketing.

The measurement and analysis of results are also essential for the effective implementation of strategic marketing planning. As cited by Ferrell and Hartline (2021), it is important to establish relevant performance indicators, such as lead conversion rate, student retention rate and return on investment in marketing. These metrics allow

evaluating the success of implemented strategies, identifying areas for improvement, and making necessary adjustments to optimize results.

Another important guideline is the establishment of an efficient management system. According to Kotler et al. (2018), it is necessary to have a clear organizational structure, assignment of responsibilities, constant monitoring of marketing actions and feedback. Efficient management guarantees the proper execution of marketing strategies and the monitoring of the results obtained.

Internal communication also plays a crucial role in the effective implementation of strategic marketing planning. As mentioned by Kotler et al. (2018), it is essential that all team members are aligned with the objectives, strategies, and marketing actions of the language school. This can be achieved through regular meetings, training and sharing relevant information.

The constant search for innovation and updating is also an important guideline for the effective implementation of strategic marketing planning. Carvalho et al. (2020) point out that it is essential to be aware of market trends, new technologies and best practices in the sector. This allows the language school to remain relevant and competitive, adapting to changes and offering innovative solutions to students.

In short, the effective implementation of strategic marketing planning in language schools requires the adoption of fundamental guidelines. These include the clear definition of organizational objectives, market analysis, market segmentation, value proposition definition, integration of marketing strategies, measurement of results, establishment of an efficient management system, internal communication, the search for innovation and constant updating. By following these guidelines, language schools are more likely to succeed in implementing their marketing strategies.

3. CONCLUSION

The effective implementation of strategic marketing planning in language schools is a complex process that requires the adoption of fundamental guidelines. Based on the analyzed studies and articles, it can be concluded that these guidelines play a crucial role in the success of the marketing strategies adopted by educational institutions. Clear definition of organizational objectives, market analysis, market segmentation, definition of value proposition, integration of marketing strategies, measurement of results, establishment of an efficient management system, internal communication and search for innovation are key elements to achieve positive results.

By establishing clear objectives, aligned with the mission and vision of the language school, the institution can direct its marketing strategies more effectively, focusing on achieving measurable results. Market analysis provides valuable insights into the characteristics and needs of the target audience, allowing the institution to adjust its marketing strategies according to market demands.

Market segmentation enables a more targeted and personalized approach, meeting the specific needs of each consumer group. By clearly communicating the value proposition, the language school highlights its competitive advantages and benefits, effectively attracting and retaining students.

The integration of marketing strategies, both online and offline, and the consistent coordination of the visual identity and institutional message, guarantee a coherent and synergistic approach in all marketing actions. The measurement and analysis of the results allow evaluating the performance of the implemented strategies, identifying areas for improvement and making necessary adjustments to optimize the results obtained.

Effective implementation of strategic marketing planning also requires an efficient management system, with clear assignment of responsibilities,

constant monitoring of marketing actions and feedback. Aligned internal communication and the constant search for innovation and updating also play key roles in the success of language schools' marketing strategies.

In summary, by following the guidelines for the effective implementation of strategic marketing planning, language schools can enhance their ability to attract, retain and meet the needs of students. The adoption of these guidelines based on academic studies and real practices contributes to strengthening the institution's image, sustainable growth, and competitive positioning in the language education market.

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